

**LANGUAGE ENVIRONMENT, LANGUAGE IDEOLOGY AND
PREJUDICE IN UZBEKISTAN.**

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Abstract. Nowadays, the linguistic environment in Uzbekistan is stable and in the phase of gradual development. Language is and should always be a basic way for society to communicate in the community, but the dominate community created a standard language that people should be using. This article presents the idea of “standard language ideology” and justifies that the problem with standard language is that it creates a sense of bias towards different types of crowds.

Keywords. Language ideology, language prejudice, standard language ideology, Chicano English, Uzbek dialects.

Introduction.

All spoken languages change over the years. Lippi-Green (2004) uses the term “language ideology” which to “domination of non-varying spoken language in the country, such as RP (UK) or SAE(USA)”. As we know there are different kind of varieties of American English (AAE, SAE, Chicano English and other regional varieties), so it is impossible to make choice about the spoken language in the country. The research which was conducted by J. Baugh in the 80s also showed dialect discrimination in the USA. Written language can be standardized across the country. Social and regional factors have great influence on the variation of language which make impossible “language ideology” in any country. The US allows citizens

to speak any language as a sign of democracy, but language discrimination can be found in some places.

Linguistic environment in Uzbekistan

Nowadays, the linguistic environment in Uzbekistan is stable and in the phase of gradual development. Uzbek linguists came together and organized an association to develop the New standardized assessment system for checking the knowledge of the Uzbek language. As we know, there are a lot of tests that are accepted internationally such as, IELTS, SAT, TOEFL. However, there was no assessment standard for testing Uzbek knowledge that could be accepted in any higher education institution. This association is working on making the "Uzbek version of IELTS", which will include four skills: speaking, reading, listening, and writing. The association accepted the Fergana dialect as a "standard language". Because, the Fergana dialect is spoken in most parts of Uzbekistan and it is known as the most understood among other dialects, which had been mostly influenced by other languages like Tajik, Turkish (Bukhara, Samarkand, Khorezm).

Language ideology and prejudice

The term standard language ideology points out the "bias toward an idealized, abstracted, and non-varying spoken language maintained by dominant institutions" (Lippi-Green, 2004). Michael Silverstein (1979) suggested a definition to the linguistic ideologies as "sets of beliefs about language articulated by users as a rationalization or justification of perceived language structure and use." Majorities of the communities select one standardized, idealized language or dialect to be spoken all over the country. For example, in the USA General American associated with the privileged white middle class is thoroughly preferred by many contexts such as media and television.

According to Lippi-Green (2004) Ideology is a "belief system" or a "body of ideas" that has little descriptive or analytical power. It is the explanation of the requirements (Eagleton, 1991) of a dominant group in a particular area. Language

prejudice is a very common attitude (Barbara Birch ,1998). "Language prejudice" is the incorrect or unjustified attitude towards an individual or a social group, race, and gender. There is another term called "standard language", which is defined as the application of double standards towards idealized and non-varying spoken language that is executed by dominant official institutions (Lippi-Green,2004). By the term "institutions" we mean the organizations that have a great impact on the current community, such as, education system, mass media, business sector, the military, and religious organizations.

The situation of Language Ideology and Language Prejudice in Uzbekistan has not changed for a long time. Fergana dialect is accepted as a standard dialect in Uzbekistan, however, all citizens residing in different regions do not have to use a standard dialect when they are invited to other formal or informal settings. Therefore, Language prejudice is not observed in almost all regions. People are accepted equally although they are speakers of different dialects. Even in the TV channels organized by different regions, most programs are shown in their dialects such as many non-official shows in "TTV" or "Samarkand" channels. It is not compulsory to utilize only standard dialect in Uzbekistan. However, in some formal settings, standard dialect should be used to become clear and comprehensible enough to the audience. If we speak in our own non-standard dialects, we are accepted politely and nobody refuse to listen to us.

Besides the Uzbek language, the Government has established the legal base for the English language as well. During the independence years, a number of legislative documents were issued to protect and develop foreign language learning in Uzbekistan. The Cabinet of Ministers issued a Resolution "On approving state educational standard on foreign languages of continuous educational system" of № 124 dated May 8, 2013 (Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, year 2013, Number 20, Article 251). As part of implementation of this Resolution, all the English classes in the country are being equipped with innovative

technologies. Moreover, as per the terms of the Resolution, the English teachers are entitled to receive a 15% premium on top of their salaries in the cities and 30% in the rural areas.

The role of Uzbek language in society.

We need to admit that it has never been paid even a little attention to the integration of four main language skills to develop our Uzbek language. This type of assessment framework serves as the main tool that demonstrates the real language abilities of the test takers. Moreover, it is true that the Uzbek language is, currently, still in the process of development and is paid much more attention to the improvement of the language. A good example can be seen in teaching the Uzbek language in the USA, Germany, Japan, South Korea, and many other developed countries which shows the increasing status of the Uzbek language worldwide. The establishment of Uzbek language testing system has been under discussion for about 4-5 years. It is, indeed, a good idea not only for local people, but also for those foreigners who want to study in Uzbek universities. As we are required to know English in certain level to be able to understand well in this University, the language proficiency requirement should be also put for our universities too.

Uzbekistan government has been giving more attention to the status of the Uzbek language in all spheres. We all know that in the last century, before Uzbekistan got its independence the use of the Russian language in Uzbekistan was propogandized by the Soviet Union. The effects of this widespread propaganda could be seen even after independence in most spheres such as in mass media, government documentation, laws, bank system. Recent regulations and policies about the improvement of the Uzbek language support the active use of it. The government is demanding to utilize the official language in all documentations of government bodies, mass media even in social aspects such as renaming the names of bars, restaurants and shops into the Uzbek language.

Conclusion.

As citizens of Uzbekistan, we haven't had such dialect discrimination so far. We also believe that people don't separate others because of their dialect or language in our country. The mentality Uzbek nation won't allow any type of discrimination including language (dialect), gender, creed, etc. There are three different varieties of Uzbek language can be found in Uzbekistan, including Karluk (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Andijan, Fergana), Kipchok (Jizzakh, Surkhandarya, Karakalpakstan, northern Khorezm), Oguz (southern Khorezm). Fergana and Tashkent dialects are considered as the standard of Uzbek language.

However, we have to admit that some unscrupulous people, especially taxi drivers and sales assistants, often try to cheat visitors from other regions. This is one of the most painful, but undeniable factors. But you can speak any variety of language wherever you go in our country. Uzbek mentality and our Constitution never allow people to judge others when they speak in different dialects. We have no right to judge people based on the way they speak, their race or creed.

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